

Effects of Using Starch at Size Press on Physical and Optical Properties of Some Packing Papers

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Abstract: In this study, fluting papers were produced by adding starch at size press (SP) and in pulp preparation unit (PP). The physical and optical properties of the papers were investigated. SP and PP papers were compared with each other to determine differences. When compared with PP papers, corrugating medium test (CMT), corrugated crush test, and ring crush test (RCT) values of SP papers (100 g/m²) were increased about 18.3%, 25.7%, and 41%, respectively. According to these results, the strength properties of papers with using size press process were better than the specified standards. Also, it was observed that the optical properties of the papers were decreased by adding starch at size press. The result showed that physical properties of fluting papers were significantly improved by adding starch at size press. Physical properties of the packaging paper are considered to be more important, size press process has an major position for packing paper manufacturer.

Keywords: size press, starch, packing paper, physical and optical properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging is an important factor for the marketing of various products and especially export goods. Productions at low cost and high strength of packing papers are significantly important as quality parameter. Paper and cardboard packing papers are the most common and environmentalists for protecting to products. The damages of paper and boards packaging to the environment are too less and easy to recycle.

Paper and cardboard used as packaging should be subjected to less deformation and included products should be less exposed to external factors during transports. For this reason, materials used in the production of paper and cardboard should have maximum strength (Casey, 1960). Due to the fact that almost all paper and cardboard are manufactured from recycled paper in Turkey, strength values of the paper and corrugated packaging can be given any desired value. Some searches are being done to increase the strength values; and one of these is starch application on the surface of papers.

Corrugated cardboard is the most popular packaging in the world for the storage and distribution of goods. Corrugated cardboard is two outside papers with a corrugated shaped paper in between. The outer papers are known as liners and the corrugated shaped paper is known as fluting or medium. Corrugated board can also be produced with two or three layers to increase its strength (Mark, 2013).

Starch application on paper surface process can be considered in three types. These are film size press, classic size press, and spray size press. Classic size press has also three types; horizontal, vertical, and angled size press as given in Fig.1 (Tunca, 2010).

Fig. 1. Types of size press a: Vertical, b: Horizontal, c: Angled size press

Sizing is a process which is mainly used for the improvement of the strength properties. Sizing is also used for reducing penetration of the aqueous solutions to the finished product. There are two different types of sizing: internal sizing and surface sizing (Smook, 1994).

Many important paper qualities can be improved with the surface treatment. Surface sizing is commonly used for the fine papers, coated base papers and paper boards (Knowpap, 2013).

In this study, fluting papers were produced by adding starch at size press (SP) and in pulp preparation unit (PP). Angled size press process was used to manufacture SP papers. The optical and physical properties of SP and PP papers were analyzed and compared with each other.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Material

In this study, fluting papers produced in Kayseri Parteks Paper Mill were used for determining the effects of size press process on the physical and optical properties. Waste papers used in production fluting papers were fluting, test liner, white liner and kraft wastes.

2.1 Methods

Fluting papers (PP) were produced with using 8, 10, 12, and 15 kg/ton starch in pulp preparation unit and strength properties of these papers were determined. The papers used 15 kg/ton starch gave the best result in physical properties. Accordingly, fluting papers, with grammages of 90, 100, 110, 125, 130, 140, 150, 160, 170, and 175 g/m², were produced with adding 15 kg/ton starch in pulp preparation unit for comparing with the SP papers.

Fluting papers (SP) were also manufactured with adding 15, 18, 22, and 26 kg/ton starch at size press and the physical properties of the papers was examined. The papers used 26 kg/ton starch gave the best results in strength values. The physical and optical properties of the SP and PP papers were compared with each other.

In order to decrease COBB (water absorptiveness) values of the papers, 8 kg/ton AKD (Alkyl ketene dimer) was added in pulp preparation unit.

The physical and optical properties of the SP and PP papers were analyzed in accordance with applicable standards given in Table 1.

Table 1. Standards of physical and optical properties

Physical and Optical Pro.	Standards	References
Grammages	TS 3122 EN ISO 536	Anon., 1998
Breaking Length (M. D.)	TS 3121-2 ISO 1924-1	Anon., 1997a
Breaking Length (C. D.)	TS 3121-2 ISO 1924-2	Anon., 1997a
CMT	TS 6717 EN ISO 7263	Anon., 2002
CCT	TS 12735	Anon., 2001a
RCT	TS 12734	Anon., 2001b
Burst Index	TS 3123 EN ISO 2759	Anon., 2004
Tear Index	TS 4423 EN 21974	Anon., 1996
ISO Brightness	ISO/DIS 2470	Anon., 1997b
ISO Opacity	ISO/DIS 2471	Anon., 1997b

*C.D: Cross Direction, M.D: Machine Direction

SEM images of the SP and PP papers were obtained using a Zeiss EVO LS-10 microscope.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical and Optical Properties of PP Papers

PP papers with grammages of 100 were produced by adding starch in certain rates in pulp preparation unit because that grammages of papers are mostly used in production of packaging. In this way, it was observed that as starch rates increased, the strength of the papers improved. In order to control paper quality, machine parameters need to be known, so the machine parameters during the production of fluting papers were given in Table 2.

According to Table 2, it was observed that the retention was improved by increasing starch rate. The physical properties of the PP papers obtained in given parameters are present in Table 3.

Table 2. The machine parameters during the paper production

Starch Rate	kg/ton	8	10	12	15
Machine Speed	m/min	280	280	280	280
Grammages	g/m ²	101	100	101	101
Width	mm	2400	2400	2360	2360
Mach.Chest Cons.	%	3.2	3.3	3.3	3.2
Mach.Chest Frns.	°SR	35	34	34	35
Headbox Cons.	%	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.03
Retention	%	78.4	79.4	80.5	81.5

Table 3. The physical properties of the PP papers

Starch Rate (kg/ton)	8	10	12	15
Grammages (g/m ²)	101	100	100	101
Tensile Index (C.D.) (Nm/g)	18.88	19.07	19.20	19.42
Tensile Index (M.D.) (Nm/g)	34.32	37.49	38.81	39.49
CMT Index (Nm ² /g)	139	144	146	150
CCT Index (Nm/g)	9.60	9.80	10.10	10.40
RCT Index (Nm/g)	4.158	4.50	4.50	4.55
Burst Index (kPam ² /g)	1.65	1.77	1.77	1.94
Tear Index (C.D) (mNm ² /g)	7.08	7.21	7.56	7.74
Tear Index (M.D) (mNm ² /g)	7.00	7.16	7.51	7.67

When Table 3 was analyzed, it is clearly seen that the maximum strength values were obtained by adding 15 kg/ton starch in pulp preparation unit, so The PP papers with different grammages were produced by adding 15 kg/ton starch in pulp preparation unit. The physical and optical properties of the PP papers were given in Table 4.

Table 4. The physical and optical properties of the PP papers with different grammages

Grammages (gr/m ²)	90	101	110	125	131	140	151	160	169	175
Tensile Index (C.D.) (Nm/g)	17.8	19.42	20.8	18.8	18.3	17	19.9	19.2	18.2	19.1
Tensile Index (M.D.) (Nm/g)	38.87	39.49	41.01	41.32	41.42	39.70	36.80	35.55	36.29	35.53
CMT Index (Nm ² /g)	146	150	183	172	194	188	195	185	178	173
CCT Index (Nm/g)	11.11	10.40	10.91	10.40	10.69	11.43	11.26	10.94	10.65	10.40
RCT Index (Nm/g)	4.44	4.55	4.45	4.56	5.34	5.57	5.96	6.25	6.57	6.46
Burst Index (kPam ² /g)	1.96	1.94	1.87	1.80	1.95	2.10	2.14	2.08	1.97	1.96
Tear Index (C.D) (mNm ² /g)	7.94	7.74	7.17	6.44	6.87	6.62	6.68	6.61	6.54	6.61
Tear Index (M.D) (mNm ² /g)	8.29	7.67	7.14	6.38	6.19	6.11	5.87	5.75	5.68	5.74
Brightness (%ISO)	24.75	25.07	22.86	26.27	24.81	25.85	30.29	29.88	28.14	24.44
Whiteness (%ISO)	25.75	34.00	31.50	35.45	33.73	35.32	39.65	39.20	37.80	33.18

The physical and optical properties of the PP papers with different grammages were found to be similar with each other in Table 4.

3.2 Physical and Optical Properties of SP Papers

SP papers with grammages of 100 were obtained by adding starch in certain rates at size pres. In this way, it was observed that as starch rates increased, the strength of the papers improved. The papers obtained by adding 26 kg/ton starch gave the best results in physical properties. In Table 5, the physical properties of the SP papers produced by adding different starch rates were presented.

Table 5. The physical properties of the SP papers

Starch Rate (kg/ton)	15	18	22	26
Grammages (g/m ²)	100	100	101	100

Tensile Index (C.D.) (Nm/g)	22.56	22.88	23.11	24.91
Tensile Index (M.D.) (Nm/g)	48.31	48.51	49.58	50.54
CMT Index (Nm ² /g)	171	172	174.3	180
CCT Index (Nm/g)	11.90	12.40	12.57	13.20
RCT Index (Nm/g)	5.8	6	6.14	6.5
Burst Index (kPam ² /g)	2.16	2.16	2.23	2.26
Tear Index (C.D) (mNm ² /g)	6.92	7.02	7.15	7.18
Tear Index (M.D) (mNm ² /g)	6.82	6.97	7.11	7.14

The SP papers with different grammages were produced by adding 26 kg/ton starch at size press. The physical and optical properties of these SP papers were given in Table 6.

Table 6. The physical and optical properties of the SP papers with different grammages

Grammages (gr/m ²)	91	100	109	126	131	139	150	161	170	176
Tensile Index (C.D.) (Nm/g)	25.6	24.9	24.0	21.3	21.0	19.4	16.2	18.3	23.5	23.0
Tensile Index (M.D.) (Nm/g)	49.58	50.54	49.79	45.66	44.97	43.55	40.75	39.80	40.00	39.38
CMT Index (Nm ² /g)	170	180	229	238	237	237	223	211	200	195
CCT Index (Nm/g)	13.63	13.20	13.12	16.51	16.03	16.69	16.20	15.90	15.41	14.49
RCT Index (Nm/g)	6.70	6.50	6.61	7.14	7.63	8.27	9.00	8.51	8.24	8.07
Burst Index (kPam ² /g)	2.26	2.26	2.34	2.33	2.40	2.40	2.42	2.20	2.12	2.07
Tear Index (C.D) (mNm ² /g)	9.08	8.63	8.2	7.85	8.23	8.03	7.78	7.42	7.17	7.14
Tear Index (M.D) (mNm ² /g)	8.87	9.88	9.28	8.32	8.45	8.28	7.82	7.36	7.22	7.18
Brightness (%ISO)	22.70	22.63	25.17	26.96	23.35	21.40	25.22	22.69	24.47	23.26
Whiteness (%ISO)	31.72	31.59	34.39	36.13	32.69	30.31	34.58	31.94	33.35	31.83

According to Table 4, the physical and optical properties of the SP papers were not significantly changed, depending on the change of grammages.

3.3 Comparison of Physical and Optical Properties of the SP and PP Papers

As shown in Fig. 2, the surface of SP papers (b) was obviously different from that of the surface of PP papers (a).

Fig. 2. SEM images of the PP (a) and SP (b) papers

In Fig. 2(a), starch was firmly distributed into the fibers and selectively combined with the negative groups of the fibers. In Fig. 2(b), starch did not penetrate into the paper, but it covered the surface of it. It can be seen how the starch bonds with the fibers and how it covers the paper surface in both of the figures.

The most important required physical properties of the packaging papers are RCT, CCT, CMT, and bursting strength (Levin and Söderhjelm, 1999; Marin et al., 2009).

– Corrugated Medium Test (CMT): measures the crushing resistance of a laboratory-fluted strip of a corrugating medium.

– Bursting strength: maximum pressure that the paper can resist without breaking with pressure applied perpendicular to the plane of the test piece.

– Corrugated Crush Test (CCT): measures the edgewise compression strength of a laboratory-fluted strip of a corrugating medium.

– Ring Crush Test (RCT): measures the resistance of a short cylinder of paper in the axial direction.

Fig. 3. CCT values of the PP (a) and SP (b) papers

Fig. 4. CMT values of the PP (a) and SP (b) papers

Fig. 5. RCT values of the PP (a) and SP (b) papers

Fig. 6. Bursting strength values of the PP (a) and SP (b) papers

The CCT, CMT, RCT, and bursting strength values of the SP and PP papers are presented in Fig. 3, 4, 5, and 6, respectively.

As shown in the figures, when compared with the PP papers, the CCT, CMT, RCT, and bursting strength value of the SP paper were increased by about 25.7%, 18.3%, 41%, and %15, respectively. Because fluting papers with grammages of 100 are the most widely used in packaging industry, values of the papers with that grammages were analyzed. The results showed that size press application obviously increased the strengths of the fluting papers. Kuusisto (2014) reported that tensile strength increased up to 108 kN/m, compared to tensile strength of 97-100 kN/m for base paper from same run without sizing.

The optical properties of the SP papers were lower than those of the PP papers. Fluting papers are used as corrugated shaped paper or medium in corrugated cardboard production. Accordingly, optical properties of fluting papers are not important for packaging paper industry.

4 CONCLUSIONS

With applying starch at size press, the physical properties of the fluting papers were improved. CCT value of the fluting paper was increased from 10.4 to 13.2 (kN/m). The other physical properties of the fluting paper such as RCT, CMT, and bursting strength were also increased.

Size press application has caused negative effects on the optical properties of fluting papers. The brightness was decreased from 25.07 to 22.63. The whiteness was also decreased by about 7.09%. Because fluting papers were used in the middle layer of corrugated cardboard, the optical properties of these papers have no importance for packaging industry.

Physical properties of packaging paper are considered to be more important than optical properties and size press applications are needed to improve physical properties of packaging papers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was supported by the Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University, Research Project Coordination Unit, under project number BAP 2012/1-2 YLS.

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